

NCAS Capel Dewi
Atmospheric Observatory
<https://amof.ac.uk/observatory/>

Minutes of the 68th Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory Users' Meeting

which was held online on 10th February 2022.

(This document was finalised on 27th July 2022)

Attendees:

(BB)	Dr Barbara Brooks ^{4,6}	Chair
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ^{4,5}	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{1,4,5}	Secretary
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ⁴	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁷	
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{2,4,5}	
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ^{4,7}	
(HP)	Dr Hannah Price ^{4,8}	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ¹	

Affiliations:

- ¹Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory (CDAO)
- ²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)
- ⁴National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)
- ⁵STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)
- ⁶University of Leeds
- ⁷University of Manchester
- ⁸Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM)

Other abbreviations used in this document:

AMDAR	Aircraft Meteorological Data Relay
BAA	British Astronomical Association
DW	Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
MST	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar)
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
PC	Personal Computer
RWP	Radar Wind Profiler
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

There were no comments on the minutes of the previous meeting.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that there now only small gaps to fill for data between June 2006 and the present. In

response to BB's enquiry, GAP reported that the only datasets from the CDAO that had been assigned Digital Object Identifier (DOIs) were those from the [Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors](#). Only a small percentage of CEDA's data holdings are actually covered by DOIs.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH to introduce a mechanism to allow users to access data files that have not yet passed quality control checks and been delivered to the CEDA archives.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he intended to make use of the [web access to JASMIN Group Work Spaces](#). However, he has not yet implemented this. BB pointed out that this was a small job and so DAH should aim to complete it by the end of March 2022.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make available the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data in NCAS-approved files through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that although he had not made direct progress on this action during the past 6 months, he was aiming to make plots of the latest WXT520 data available through the [supplementary CDAO website](#) as a stepping stone. Plots of the latest LD40 data are already made available in this way. The background to this decision will be covered in section 4.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had had no time to work on this action during the past 6 months. He pointed out that the information contained within these files would be of very niche interest.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made some progress on this action as a result of work he had been obliged to undertake in order to replace a failed processing PC. This has revealed how he can re-create the legacy python environment for which the MST radar processing software was written. He will give a full report of this in section 4.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to arrange for installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton staff, for the latter part of 2019.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this action had primarily been held up by Covid-19 restrictions on international travel (the company that will install the transmitters is based in Australia). CJW noted that the new mechanism for transferring funds from NCAS to STFC (including those allotted for this action) had now been established. He thought that it was relatively easy to add a budget line, as long as the funding was from NERC.

ACTION ITEM 64.2.1 DAH and GAP to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar available through CEDA.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he was in discussions with the Met Office regarding which licence should be used for making the statistics files available through CEDA. EGN indicated that she would like to have access to the equivalent comparison statistics for data from the Radar Wind Profiler (RWP). Although she has been sending data to **E-PROFILE**, they had not been appearing on the system. It turns out that this is because the files for the low and high modes are being deposited in separate sub folders rather than together in a higher-level folder. Although the E-PROFILE system used to be able to deal with this situation, it had stopped being able to do so at some point. However, the issue was resolved in January 2022.

ACTION ITEM 65.3.1 DAH to make enquires about the possibility of installing a fibre broadband connection to the CDAO.

COMPLETED

DAH will provide further details in section 3c.

ACTION ITEM 67.3.1 DAH to arrange for the replacement of the structures that house the MST Radar's primary power splitters as soon as possible.

ONGOING

DAH will report on progress in section 3d.

ACTION ITEM 67.4.1 DAH to visit Frongoch as soon as possible in order to resolve the problem of invalid direction values.

COMPLETED

DAH will provide further details in section 4b.

3. Observatory Report

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at <https://mst.nerc.ac.uk/EVENTS/>.

3a) Data Management

GAP reported that data from the CDAO can now be accessed through a directory structure based on NCAS naming conventions, i.e. <https://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/ncas-cdao/data>, as well as through the one based on legacy naming conventions, i.e. <https://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/mst/data/>. The link to version 4 MST Radar data products through the new structure does not currently work and so the dataset must be accessed using the legacy directory path of <https://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/mst/data/nerc-mstrf-radar-mst/v4-0/st-mode/cardinal>.

EGN asked why a bulk download option was no longer available through CEDA web pages. GAP explained that this functionality (and the zip download option) had not been ported to the new system since it was simpler to use the `wget` command. Details of the appropriate syntax can be found by following the shopping trolley link within a directory that contains data files. This new way of navigating the CEDA archive is becoming standardised across all datasets. The same approach is already available for EGN's RWP at <https://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/ncas-mobile/data/ncas-radar-wind-profiler-1>. It will soon be applied to data from the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory. DAH noted that the name used for the MST Radar within the new structure is `ncas-mst-radar-1`, rather than `ncas-radar-mst-1`, which would be more-consistent with the names used for other NCAS instruments.

3b) Electricity - DAH

DAH reported that all NERC sites have had their electricity accounts transferred from British Gas to EDF. This occurred on 1st April 2021 for the CDAO. However, DAH is still waiting to receive the first

bill almost 12 months later (he used to receive bills monthly). DAH has submitted meter readings taken on 1st April 2021, 5th November 2021, and 28th January 2022. EDF would like to install some sort of smart meter at the site, so that readings do not have to be taken manually. However, poor mobile phone reception at the site will be a limiting factor. This is also a problem for NERC, who would like to install electricity monitoring devices at all of their sites.

Portable Appliance Testing (PAT) was carried out at the CDAO on 3rd December 2021. This task had been delayed by Covid-19 restrictions.

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units switched to battery power in response to a brief input power problem at 03:44 UTC on 18th July 2021. DAH used to receive e-mail notifications from the UPS units at least every two weeks when self tests were undertaken. However, he has not received any notifications since the ones on 18th July 2021. He wondered if this had something to do with the UPS units somehow relying on the presence of PC that failed in September 2021 (see section 4).

DAH ordered a new set of batteries for one of the UPS units in mid December 2021.

3c) Telecommunications

The broadband modem lost its internet connection shortly after 05:21 UTC on 3rd January 2022, which was a Bank Holiday. DAH suspects that this was the result of a thunder storm since [the MST Radar data appear to show deep convection at this time](#). Dave Wareing (DW) happened to be on site later in the day and power-cycled the modem at around 12:00 UTC. This restored the connection.

The contract for installation of a fibre broadband connection to the CDAO became active on 15th September 2021. It could take up to a year for the work to be completed. Openreach have recently (21st January 2022) informed DAH that it is the responsibility of the property owner to install a cable trench between the road and building where the broadband connection is required. This covers a distance of almost 100 m in the case of the CDAO. LD has been investigating whether the person who cuts the grass at the site might be able to dig the cable trench.

GV reported that the phone line to the lidar container has been discontinued. However, DW would like to install an internet cable so that the container can be linked to one of the networks within the bungalow. This will require a cable trench to be dug between the container and the bungalow.

3d) Miscellaneous

The septic tank was supposed to be emptied on Friday 30th July 2021. However, the person responsible did not get to the area until late in the afternoon, by which time there was no-one on site.

DAH reported that he had attended the online E-PROFILE meeting on 8th and 10th November 2021. These meetings now cover laser ceilometers as well as wind-profiling radars. DAH pointed out that it would be hard to justify the time and expense of attending one of these meetings in person and so he was pleased that they could be attended virtually.

DAH held a meeting with NERC and their Facilities Management suppliers on 21st December 2021 to discuss the replacement of the "chicken shacks". An initial contract has been set up by NERC just to create designs for the replacement shacks and to find a suitable sub-contractor to carry out the work. The designs are based on use of treated plywood for the roof panels. However, DAH had originally suggested using Glass Reinforced Plastic, which he thought was likely to be more durable. DAH confirmed that he would have the final say on which materials would be used.

DAH is aiming to arrange for the installation of a new concrete instrument pad through the same Facilities Management suppliers. LD suggested that the best location for the new pad would be between

the existing ones for the RWP and for the mobile laboratory. There is a slight gradient between the two areas. GV recommended that the new pad should be horizontal, with step changes at either side, rather than sloping. LD also pointed out that he would like to get a cable duct installed between the new pad and the bungalow. He was slightly concerned that existing, buried cables could be impacted by removing the top soil from where the new pad would be installed.

BB asks if there was any other estates work that needed to be carried out at the CDAO, e.g. the track and the car parking area. GV and LD thought that these were in sufficiently good condition for the amount of use that they receive. LD thought that the fencing around the LD40 instrument compound might need to be looked at at some point in the medium term.

4. CDAO Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at <https://mst.nerc.ac.uk/EVENTS/>.

DAH began this section by reporting that the PC “claudius” responsible for all file transfers, as well as for processing the latest MST Radar data, had failed shortly after 17:31 local time on Friday 17th September 2021. It had been in operation for approximately 15 years. Although this failure did not stop the MST Radar from running, it had an impact on virtually all other operations at the CDAO. It took DAH 4 weeks to get all of the necessary processes running on a replacement PC “germanicus”, which he had installed at the site in 2018 after PC claudius had suffered from a temporary problem.

In order to restart the supply of MST Radar wind-profile data to E-PROFILE as soon as possible, DAH decided to recreate the python environment (2.3) used on PC claudius (using a modern python environment would have been a more forward-looking approach, but would have required fundamental changes to be made to the data processing software). He had had partial success with this approach back in 2018, when PC germanicus had been installed, but had given up after he was unable to get one of the modules to compile. It turns out that this was the result of the way in which a different module, upon which the failed module depended, had been compiled. However, the error message was sufficiently subtle that DAH would not have been able to make any progress without help from a member of CEDA's technical staff. This allowed him to start processing the backlog of MST Radar data on Wednesday 29th September and to restart the data feed to E-PROFILE on Friday 1st October.

It took DAH another two weeks (i.e. until 14th October) to get all of the processes back in operation, e.g. producing plots of the latest 24 hours' worth of data. He took the opportunity to introduce some targeted improvements. For example, he has simplified the structure of the [supplementary website](#), made the links more accessibility-compliant, and changed the branding from NERC MSTRF to NCAS CDAO. The plots of LD40 plots are now updated every 10 minutes rather than every 30 minutes. All plots now contain embedded metadata. DAH would like to add plots of the latest surface met data from the Vaisala WXT520.

CJW pointed out that there should be a programme of planned replacement for older computers. BB recommended replacing PCs as soon as they are out of their warranty period. GAP reported that CEDA holds a central record of the computers that they operate and of their required software and services. BB reported that creating a register of this type for NCAS would be one of the responsibilities for the new IT Support role.

On the subject of accessibility, BB recommended that DAH speak to HMAR about colour-blind-friendly colour maps. She would like to see these used across NCAS. CJW pointed out that there are different types of colour-blindness, which makes it difficult to find a colour map that works for everyone. He thought that the Homeyer rainbow map was better than most, but still not perfect. Ideally plots could be created on demand with the user specifying the choice of colour map. GV commented that he would

like to see plots of the latest Frongoch data made available through the supplementary website.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

The tipping bucket rain gauge recorded a single tip at 05:00 UTC on 27th August 2021, which appears to be the result of dew accumulation. The following tips appear to be the result of melting frost: 10:40 UTC on 22nd November 2021, 11:00 UTC on 19th December 2021, 11:00 UTC on 14th January 2022, 11:00 UTC on 17th January 2022, and 09:50 UTC on 30th January 2022. These measurements have not been removed from the data products files available through CEDA.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

DAH visited Frongoch with LD on 7th September 2021 in order to address action item 67.4.1. He was not sure whether the problem of recorded wind directions remaining close to 30° since October 2019 was the result of an issue with the wind vane, the data logger, or the connecting cable. However, thinking that the data logger was most likely to be the source of the problem, he purchased a new unit prior to his visit. Consequently, he was surprised to find that the existing logger now appeared to be giving realistic readings. It was fortuitous that, on the day of his visit, the sustained winds were southerly and that they were fluctuating by up to 90 ° either side of this as a result of the low wind speeds. It was also crucial that LD was with him, since this allowed one of them to monitor the logger whilst the other monitored the wind vane. On a previous visit to Frongoch, DAH had been hampered by the fact that time scales for fluctuations in wind direction were far shorter than the time taken for him to run between the logger and a location from which he could see the wind vane.

From DAH's subsequent examination of the raw data files, it appears that the recorded directions reverted to realistic-looking values on 18th March 2021. No intervention had been made at around this time and so the cause of the problem remains a mystery.

DAH has always been uncertain as to whether the CR1000X data logger synchronises its clock when it establishes a mobile data connection (the previous logger used to do this via its dial-up connection). Campbell Scientific were unable to answer this question, but pointed out that the internal clock is considerably more accurate than those found within most electronic devices (which typically drift by a few tens of seconds a month). DAH was surprised to find that, during his 7th September 2021 visit, the clock appeared to be on time (at least to within a second or two) after two years of operation. Nevertheless, he is still uncertain whether this is down to synchronisation or inherent accuracy.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

DAH reported that he had had no time to deal with the data from this instrument since the last meeting. However, he is keen to make plots of the latest 24 hours' worth of data available through the supplementary website. BB reported that she had a number of WXT520s and that she made use of [Grafana software for visualisation](#).

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH reported that there have been no issues with this instrument during the past 6 months.

4e) Lufft Ceilometer

HMAR reported that this instrument is working well. There have been a few small issues, which might have been the result of network problems. The instrument's window does not need to be cleaned as frequently as the one for an identical instrument based in Manchester. HMAR is currently writing python software to allow him to access the raw data and to create NCAS-compliant netCDF data files. BB encouraged HMAR to be in a position to produce netCDF files by the end of March 2022.

4f) Sky Cameras

DAH reported that he had backed up the photos from this instrument to an external hard drive when he visited the CDAO in September 2021.

4g) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH reported that he had used photos taken by the NLC Camera at the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory for a novel purpose. Judith Jeffery has been attempting to identify the signature of fog in measurements made by the [PWS100 Present Weather Sensor](#). DAH had noticed that fog was sometimes seen during the dawn in photos taken by the NLC camera. The fog can either be confined to a layer that appears to be no more than a few tens of cm thick (e.g. as seen on 16th July 2021) or can exist in a wider layer that appears to be at least 10 m deep (e.g. as seen on 11th July 2021). In the examples referred to above, the [visibility measurements made by the PWS100](#) are lower in the deep fog case than in the shallow fog case.

DAH has been invited to give an online talk on NLCs and Polar Mesosphere Summer Echoes (PMSEs) to the [Radio Astronomy Section of the British Astronomical Association \(BAA\)](#) in March 2022. The BAA is an organisation for amateur astronomers.

4h) MST Radar

DAH reported that during the past 6 months, there has been only one instance of the MST Radar experiencing a raised noise floor: between 04:50 and 07:00 UTC on [27th September 2021](#). Such instances lead to a loss in useful altitude coverage rather than to unreliable values and so are released to the CEDA archive as they are. In the case of the following problems, the files are labelled as containing suspect data.

There was one case of contamination by an unknown signal: between 04:40 and 06:20 UTC on [19th December 2021](#) at altitudes between 4.5 and 9.0 km and above 14 km. Wind speeds were unrealistically fast compared to those at adjacent times and altitudes in two cases: between 20:30 and 21:20 UTC on [30th January 2022](#) at around 17.5 km, and between 16:40 and 17:00 UTC on 1st February 2022 at around 2.5 km.

A communications problem between the radar control and beam steering PCs caused the radar beam to be stuck in a single pointing direction (probably SW6.0) between 19:57 UTC on [6th January 2022](#) and 08:25 UTC on the following morning. Although DAH restarted the radar at 08:25, the problem persisted, albeit with the radar beam now stuck in the Vertical pointing direction. Consequently, DAH rebooted both the radar control and beam steering PCs before restarting the radar at 09:36 UTC on [7th January 2022](#).

In response to GAP's question, DAH confirmed that files labelled as containing suspect data are identified subjectively. In DAH's opinion, this is not a problem in that the files so labelled definitely contain suspect data. The limitation of this subjective process is that there may be some files that contain suspect data that DAH has failed to identify. BB asked DAH to make sure his quality control procedures are documented. This is required for instruments across NCAS. CJW pointed out that it would be good to have a central instrument performance log for all instruments.

5. Guest Instrument Report

DAH reported that Ben Pickering is due to visit the CDAO on 18th March 2022 in order to collect the laser disdrometer that he had used for his PhD studies.

Jon Jones from the Met Office has contacted DAH to enquire about the possibility of installing a new GPS receiver at the CDAO. The existing receiver is quite old and no longer contributes to the Met Of-

face's operational network.

EGN reported that her efforts to upgrade the RWP had been slowed down by Covid-19 restrictions and by Brexit. The PCA computer has finally been upgraded to one running Windows 10. It has more memory, which means that it can sample more range gates. The PCT computer has also been replaced, although the old one has been kept for running reprocessing jobs. Problems with data transfers between the PCA and PCT computers have now been resolved. The biggest problem has been logging on to the computers remotely. This can no longer be done using TeamViewer and VNC is not good enough. EGN is now using [LogMeIn](#), which requires a licence.

There has been an intermittent issue with the beam getting stuck in a single pointing direction. Although this could be cleared by rebooting the system, it was inconvenient when it occurred during a period of interest, e.g. during Storm Arwen on 26th/27th November 2021. The beam steering switch was replaced on 17th December.

The system appears to be more reliable with the new PCT computer. There have been lots of good observations, with examples of storms, thermals, boundary layer structures, and possibly even insects (on 9th July 2021). EGN has started to compare wind data from the RWP and from the MST Radar. As a result of the RWP upgrade, the altitude extent overlapped by the two radars has increased.

In response to BB's enquiries about whether the data were being made available through CEDA, EGN clarified that she is able to create files following version 1 of the NCAS standard. However, she has not yet updated her software to be compliant with version 2. BB recommended that EGN should focus on the version 1 standard until all issues have been resolved. BB will introduce EGN to Josh, a new data specialist at NCAS, who should be able to help her to create version 2 files.

LD asked whether there might be a benefit in producing a wind-profile product derived from a combination of MST Radar and RWP data. This would have a larger altitude extent than the data from either instrument alone. BB asks whether there was a need for such a product. EGN pointed out that if the plots for the two instruments were made available alongside each other, anyone who was interested in combining the data would be able to see that this is possible. GAP indicated that he could create links between the two existing datasets through their CEDA catalogue pages.

CJW noted that most attendees of the CDAO Users' meetings are producers rather than users of data. DAH pointed out that since the data from the CDAO were openly-accessible through CEDA, there is no way for him to identify who the main users are. GAP clarified that 19 users have accessed CDAO data through CEDA during the past year.

GV gave a report on the lidars. The Elight and the large lidar have both undergone repairs. However, there has been so much cloud cover over the past winter that there have been few opportunities for testing the systems. The water vapour lidar, which is due to be used for HP's forthcoming campaign, was given a test run during the evening of 12th January 2022. Useful data were available for altitudes up to 6 km from an accumulation of two and a half hours of observations. The instrument would need to be operated all night in order to yield useful data up to 10 km. GV compared the data with measurements made by radiosondes. This was made slightly difficult by the fact that the humidity measurements varied considerably from sonde to sonde. However, there was fairly good agreement for the saturation humidity, which will be the product of primary interest for HP.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Mode S temperatures - GV

DW began the collection of Mode S atmospheric data from aircraft as something of a hobby project. GV

has analysed the data and thinks that they could actually be quite useful. He is particularly interested in being able to calculate the vertical temperature gradient, which is needed together with MST radar spectral widths to determine the turbulence eddy dissipation rate.

DW has built a Mode S receiving system using open-source [PiAware software](#). It is in operation at Frongoch and is configured to record data at 30 s intervals.

Temperature is not measured directly, but derived from the Mach number, i.e. the ratio of the speed of the aircraft to the temperature-dependent speed of sound. The raw temperature data are very “noisy”, since they are combined from different aircraft, and so need to be averaged. Since GV is primarily interested in the broad-scale value rather than in a spot measurement, this is not a problem. The data contain some spectacular outliers and so filtering is necessary, e.g. by restricting interest to the interquartile range.

For the 2021 year as a whole, the daily number of data points increased noticeably after January, when lockdown restrictions were eased. There was a reduction after August, when the peak summer holiday season came to an end. There is a diurnal variation in availability, with a peak during the morning and very low numbers during the night. The main flight lanes are E-W across south Wales and N-S across central England. There are very few flights close to Aberystwyth and these tend to be made during the night. GV has found that 4000 - 5000 measurements are required to generate a decent temperature profile, which covers the altitude range 4 - 14 km. He has concentrated on data from flights that pass within a 200 km radius of Frongoch. If the search radius is reduced to 100 km, the number of data points drops markedly.

GV has evaluated the representativeness of the data by making comparisons with radiosonde profiles. The mean temperature differences were lowest for comparisons made with radiosondes from Camborne. The standard deviations of the differences were lower for comparisons made with radiosondes from the closest launch site at Aberporth. However, there appears to be a systematic bias. It's not yet clear if this is real, since there were relatively few profiles available from this site. The mean differences were lowest for comparisons made against the output from [the ManUniCast model](#). This has led David Schultz (at the University of Manchester) to suggest that the model output might actually be a better source of data for calculating the vertical temperature gradient.

BB asked whether the quality of the data might improve as the number of flights bounces back after Covid-19 restrictions. GV reported that he has not seen much change recently, although the number of flights might increase over the summer holiday season. HP asked whether the type of sensor being used could be identified. GV clarified that each data messages give a unique aircraft name and flight number, so individual aircraft can be tracked. However, there is no information about the type of sensor being used. Moreover, the sensors do not appear to be carefully calibrated. The data from some aircraft are consistently biased high whilst the data from other aircraft are consistently biased low. GAP reported that [AMDAR \(Aircraft Meteorological Data Relay\) data are available through CEDA](#) and wondered if these might be use. GV clarified that he had not investigated AMDAR data, although there are papers comparing them with those from Mode S.

7. Any Other Business

GV reported that there was not much to update on Aberystwyth University's proposed [Spectrum Centre](#). The town of Aberystwyth as a whole is due to receive a substantial amount of investment from the UK Government's levelling up scheme and from the Welsh Legislative Assembly. Although some money has been reserved for the Spectrum Centre, no-one yet knows how this will be used. It will take some time for this money to become available. The University would like to make use of a number of sites in west Wales, including the Capel Dewi site. The University has already employed one lecturer with

relevant interests and is looking to appoint a professor.